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(1)–(3),

(1)–(3)

$$p_{ij}^p = \sum_{l=1}^l \delta_l \left(\frac{q_{ijl}^p}{l} \right)^{C_l}, \quad (1)$$

$$K_{ij}^p = \frac{p_{ij}^p}{ij} \left(1 + \frac{H_{ij}}{H_{max}} + \frac{E_{ij}}{E_{max}} \right), \quad (2)$$

$$\delta_l = \begin{cases} 0, & q_{ijl}^p < 0,5 \\ 1, & q_{ijl}^p \geq 0,5 \end{cases}, \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & : \frac{p_{ij}^p}{ij} - (i,j) - ; \\ K_{ij}^p - & (i,j) - ; \\ q_{ijl}^p - & l - - (i,j); l - \end{aligned}$$

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2.

 $ij/H_{max} + E_{ij}/E_{max}$

(2),

 E_{ij} , ij .

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 $\frac{ij}{E_{ij}/E_{max}}$

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5. q_{ijl}^p -86,

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(1)-(3)

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(4)-(6).

(k)

(z),

(e).

(k)

(d)

$$k = f(z, e, d).$$

(4)

(2)

(k)

$$k = z \left(\alpha + \beta \frac{e}{e_{\max}} + \gamma \frac{d}{d_{\max}} \right),$$

(5)

: α, β, γ -

$$; \max - (,); d_{max} -$$

$$(g) \quad (k)$$

$$(k)$$

$$g = \sum_{(p,q) \in (s-s)} k_{pq} \cdot \frac{R-d_{spq}}{R} + \sum_{(p,q) \in s} k_{pq} \cdot \frac{R-d_{spq}}{R} \cdot \frac{d_{pq}}{R}, \quad (6)$$

$$: s - ; R - ; s_c - , d_{spq} - (p,q).$$

$$(4)-(6)$$

(19),

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(7)-

F,

$$F = F(A) = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} \cdot b_{ij} \cdot g_{ij}(A) \rightarrow \max, \quad (7)$$

: mxn -

() mxn ; -

$$a_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & (i, j) \\ 0, & \end{cases}; \quad (8)$$

B -

$$b_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & (i, j) \\ 0, & \end{cases}; \quad (9)$$

$g_{ij}(A) - (i,j),$

$$g_{ij}(A) = \sum_{(p,q) \in (s_{ij}-s_{ij})} k_{pq}(A) \cdot \frac{R-d_{spq}}{R} + \sum_{(p,q) \in s_{ij}} k_{pq}(A) \cdot \frac{R-d_{spq}}{R} \cdot \frac{d_{pq}(A)}{R}, \quad (10)$$

$$: s_{ij} - (i,j), ; d_{ij}() -$$

$$d_{ij}(A) = \min \left(\sqrt{(x_k - x_{ij})^2 + (y_k - y_{ij})^2} \right), \quad k = \overline{1, N'}; \quad (11)$$

$$N - (x_k, y_k) \quad (N) \quad ; \quad C - N \quad ;$$

$$(x_{ij}, y_{ij}) - (i, j); \quad k_{ij}(A) -$$

$$(i, j), \quad :$$

$$k_{ij}(A) = z_{ij} \left(\alpha + \beta \frac{e_{ij}}{e_{\max}} + \gamma \frac{d_{ij}(A)}{d_{\max}(A)} \right), \quad (12)$$

: $\alpha, \beta, \gamma -$

$$(\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1); \quad e_{ij} -$$

$$e_{\max} = \max_{b_{ij}=1} (e_{ij}), \quad i = \overline{1, m}, \quad j = \overline{1, n}; \quad (13)$$

$d_{\max}(A) -$

$$d_{\max}(A) = \max_{b_{ij}=1} (d_{ij}(A)), \quad i = \overline{1, m}, \quad j = \overline{1, n}; \quad (14)$$

$z_{ij} -$

$$z_{ij} = \sum_{p=1}^t \left(\frac{q_{ij p}}{p} \right)^{C_p}, \quad (15)$$

: $q_{ij} -$

$(i, j);$

; $C -$

$C = 1, 7;$

$- 1, 3;$

$- 1, 0;$

$- 0, 9; \quad t -$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} \leq N, \quad (16)$$

$$d_{ij}(A) \geq d_{\min} \quad \forall (i, j) \quad a_{ij} = 1, \quad (17)$$

: $N -$

; $d_{\min} -$

$d_{ij}(A)$

$V:$

$$V = \begin{cases} 0, \\ 1, \end{cases}$$

. (18)

1) $F(A) = \{d_{ij}(A)\}$ (1), $g_{ij}(A)$

2) b_{ij} (9), F (7),
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(19) 3) (11) (17) , , (7)-(19)
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" (Drop algorithm),
(Maranzana algorithm), (Teitz-Bart algorithm Bump-
and-Shift algorithm), GRIA (Global-Regional Interchange Approach,
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(7)-(19)
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():

1. $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, N, N, d_{min}, d, R,$
 $(x_k, y_k), k = \overline{1, N}$

2. $V;$

3. $N_{copy}=N;$

4. $q_{ijl}, l = \overline{1, t}, i = \overline{1, m}, j = \overline{1, n} ;$

5. $z_{ij}, e_{ij}, i = \overline{1, m}, j = \overline{1, n} ;$

6. $e_{max};$

7. $g_{max}=0;$

8. $d_{ij} V, i = \overline{1, m}, j = \overline{1, n} ;$

9. $d_{max};$

10. $k_{ij}, i = \overline{1, m}, j = \overline{1, n} ;$

11. $g_{ij}, i = \overline{1, m}, j = \overline{1, n} ;$

12. $g_{max}=\max(g_{ij}), i = \overline{1, m}, j = \overline{1, n} \quad d_{ij} > d_{min} \quad b_{ij}=1;$

13. $N_{copy}=N \quad g_{max}=0,$
 . 17;

14. $N_{copy} > N \quad g_{max}=0,$
 . 17;

15. $(i, j). N=N-I;$

16. $N > 0,$. 6.

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k-

(x_k, y_k)

d_{min}

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$(k-I)-$

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$(k^* - (k^*-I) -) ,$

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k* $(k^*-I)-$,

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(i j,

$i = \overline{1, N'}, j = \overline{1, N'}, i < j$)

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$(i^* \quad j^*, i^* = \overline{1, N'}, j^* = \overline{1, N'}, i^* \neq j^*)$

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 $R^2=0,6033$

$$T(N, X) = 34,14N + 0,04X + 1199,22. \quad (20)$$

$R^2=0,5997$

$$T(N, X) = 34,68N + 0,05X + 1185,76. \quad (21)$$

$R^2=0,7569$

$$T(N, X) = 1644,18N + 0,67X^2 - 0,28X - 7346,82. \quad (22)$$

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(7)-(19) — (2), 2-4
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AISEEM
Microsoft Access,
Borland C++ Builder 6.0, ADO (ActiveX Data Objects),
SQL
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TPlant, TWind) 10 (TFormMain,
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ABSTRACT

rtemchuk V. O. Mathematical and computer tools for solving the placement of observation points network monitoring air. – Manuscript.

The thesis of dissertation for a Candidate's degree in Technical Sciences n specialty 01.05.02 – Mathematical modeling and numerical methods. – Pukhov Institute for Modelling in Energy Engineering, NAS of Ukraine, K iv, 2011.

The paper presents a model of information utility for making observations in area and describes a mathematical formulation of the problem of optimal placement of observation points network monitoring air. The new formulation uses the proposed model of information utility and, unlike existing counterparts, meets the basic requirements of modern national and international legislation, which allows forming networks monitoring air depending on the purpose of their operation, types of observation points etc.

Methods and related algorithms are developed to solve the task. The algorithms are based on greedy algorithm and its combination with the method of exhaustive search, which allows quick finding close to optimal or optimal solution.

The algorithms are implemented as part of specialized information-analytical system for environmental and energy monitoring (AISEEM). Also research and testing of algorithms are conducted to calculate the time needed to solve the task and obtain the optimal solution. The result of the research shows that the use of proposed algorithms provides the efficient implementation of computer software for solving the problem of placement of observation points network monitoring air.

Keywords: network monitoring air, numerical methods, greedy algorithm, an exhaustive search method, database, environmental maps, information-analytical system.

